

Impact Factor: 8.67

ISSN:0976-8165

THE CRITERION

AN INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL IN ENGLISH

Bi-Monthly Peer-Reviewed eJournal

16 YEARS OF OPEN ACCESS

VOL. 16 ISSUE-4, AUGUST 2025

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ISSN 2278-9529

Galaxy: International Multidisciplinary Research Journal
www.galaxyimrj.com

Exploitation of Nature and Displacement of Tribal People: A Study of Ecological Agonies in Jacinta Kerketta's Selected Poems

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Article History: Submitted-31/07/2025, Revised-14/08/2025, Accepted-19/08/2025, Published-31/08/2025.

Abstract:

Recent environmental degradation and challenges related to ecological disruption, climate issues as well as displacement have significantly affected both humans and non-human entities on the Earth. This situation evokes feelings of sorrow and mourning, particularly for Adivasi people whose livelihoods are rely on natural world and who maintain a close profound connection with the natural environment. Exploitation of natural environments and destruction of natural habitats of different living species driven by different self- interested groups for the purpose of industrial expansion, urbanization, logging and mining, poses a significant threat to biodiversity and healthy ecosystems. This study aims to explore ecological disruption and ecological agonies illustrated by the poet Jacinta Karketta in her selected poems. The analysis is to highlight the environmental devastation and displacements of tribal people from their root of existence as a consequence of unchecked industrial progress. This paper attempts to trace the concern for environmental degradation and ecological disruption through the concept of ecocriticism. The purpose is also to shed light on how the egocentric attitude has violated the bond between man and natural world, and thereby rendering nature a victim, and leading to dire consequences for human survival.

Keywords: Exploitation of nature, Tribal people, Environmental disruption, Ecocriticism, Ecology.

Introduction:

Ecocriticism examines interactions between human beings and natural world, particularly how man's relationship with the physical environment reflected in literature. It is a recent critical approach, which originated in North America emerged in the early 1990s. It becomes a new branch of literary criticism to examine the mutual relations between man and environment. The term ecocriticism, first introduced in 1978 by William Rueckert in his essay titled "Literature and Ecology: An experiment in Ecocriticism". By ecocriticism Rueckert meant "the application of ecology and ecological concepts to the study of literature. (Glotfelty, xviii-xix) Literature can play a great role in reflecting present environmental issues through literary texts. Kerketta selects poetry as a powerful platform for expressing and addressing the issues faced by the Adivasi community and concerns related to the loss of natural resources, because poetry possess "the energy and power" to appeal "the human community" irrespective of race, class or gender (Rueckert, 109). Previously Researchers have addressed the issue of the environmental degradation, the deplorable plight of tribal people, as a result of mining activities, urbanization and infrastructure projects. However, this study aims to highlight the agonies, cries and sufferings experienced by both the nature and tribal people emphasizing their ecological significance. For Adivasi people nature is the integral part to their identity. From time immemorial their ancestors are living harmoniously with nature, a connection that is deeply embedded in their belief system, culture and their way of life. It is their way of living which helps them to believe that nature is an integral part of their existence rather a separate entity. The destruction of nature in the name of development adversely affected indigenous communities. In the Bible, the description of the 'Garden of Eden' shows that human life and nature are inseparable (Rakshit, 201). The emergence of Tribal Literature had its genesis in the

conservation of nature, as the tribal movements focused on safeguarding their cultural heritage, their intrinsic ways of living, and their deep relationships with ‘forest, land and water’. However, it is not only a profound loss for the Adivasi people when they are compelled and forcefully leave their loved forests, lands and habitats against their will, but nature itself also bemoans over the displacement and loss of her people. The writers belonging to the Tribal Community have highlighted the interconnected relationships between nature and tribal existence, emphasizing that nature cannot be separated from tribal way of life. The Indigenous population of India, officially called “Scheduled Tribes,” comprises more than 700 different communities. According to the last census data in 2011, 8.6% of India’s total population (more than 100 million people) is made up of adivasis, literally translated as first inhabitants or original dwellers, and are the world’s largest population of Indigenous people (Faizi & Nair, 2016). They protect and conserve nature not only because it provides them life sustenance materials but they regard nature as a sacred entity. As XAXA points out: “The bonds between the earth and the tribes are not only material but also moral and ritualistic. Land is valuable to the tribes not only because it provides them the means of survival and livelihood but also because it was bequeathed to them by their ancestors” (Rakshit, 204). Biodiversity loss, disruption of ecosystem and degradation of environment represent a significant trajectory toward the complete annihilation of all living species including humanity. Barry Commoner has called this “the first law of ecology.” It is the principle that everything in the natural world is interconnected with one another (Phemister, 239).

Jharkhand, East Singbhum, a state located in the eastern part of the country, India, recognized as the birthplace of the poet Jacinta Kerketta. The poet was born in the Oraon community and is educated and living in Jharkhand. In the country Jharkhand occupies first position in terms of coal reserves, second for iron, third for copper ore reserves, seventh for bauxite reserves. Furthermore, this tremendous mineral resource seems to have become one of the leading causes

of environmental degradation and displacement of Adivasi people in this region of the country (Bhattacharjee and Singh, 165). The theme of his poems encompasses the exploitation and degradation of natural environment, miserable plight faced by Adivasi people, issues of displacement, instances of discrimination and the mining activities conducted by the industrial groups in the region. Among her many nature poems six poems have been selected to discuss ecological agonies in this paper, five from "Angor" (2016) namely, "The River that was", "Bloodstained rivers" "The dust of development", "The blossoms of Saranda", "O city!" and one from "Land of The Roots". The poet addressed the problem of environmental degradation stemming from indiscreet mining activities and examines its impact on the physical environment, highlighting the avaricious and insensitive attitude of money-grubbing group of people towards nature. The issues like climate change and environmental degradation are rooted in ego-consciousness. The growing avaricious for more money, power, among selfish group of people leads to the exploitation of natural resources and basic elements like air, water, food which sustains life on this earth. In pursuit of development their greed leads them overlook the impending threat of the complete annihilation of human civilization. Krutch rightly says that, "We have engineered ourselves into a position where for the first time in history, it has become possible for man to destroy his whole species...." (Glen, 232). Karketta's poetry embodies issues like environmental exploitation, displacement of indigenous people and laments over the ecological devastation.

Objectives:

This study seek to explore the environmental degradation and sufferings faced by the natural world including its flora and fauna as well as indigenous community, as a result of development projects and mining activities through ecological approach. At the same time, an effort has been made to spread ecological awareness and to encourage sustainable development practice by highlighting the deplorable plight of nature and Adivasi people.

Methodology:

A close study of primary and secondary sources has been conducted from various journals and books chapters. The research has employed qualitative technique, specifically content analysis framed within the concept of ecocriticism, to investigate the ecological anguish, the miserable plight, faced by natural environment and Adivasi people.

The poet articulates concerns regarding the degradation of the mother nature, highlighting the disrupted interdependent relationship between man and nature, resulted from the displacement of indigenous communities due to mining activities, which has adversely affected the biodiversity, natural ecosystem as well as tribal well-being. The greedy industrial demon has devoured the lush green land, and attack on the lives of tribal people, and uprooted those people who had been living harmoniously with nature for hundreds of years. The agonies of nature, including her flora and fauna, is evident in the poem, “The River that was”, as the poet narrates:

“Those gurgling waters of Pusaro river

Were once my cradle,

On her lap I had bounced, in her ripples I had played.

Today I see

The ever thirsty, flickering, slavering, devilish tongue

Of the growing population

Has dried up all those waters” (Kerketta1- 8).

In this poem, the poet reflects on cherished memories and tells us an account of loss, loss of past bliss which she experienced within the natural world. The lines suggest that the poet perceives the river as her mother figure, reflecting on her experiences of playing and finding joy in the

lap of the mother River Pusaro. The gurgling of the waters of the river denotes that the river was once happy and vigorous. The river was full of life. The poet mourns over the miserable condition of her mother river, whose existence has been stifled by the treacherous forces of progress. The poem captured the cruel account in details faced by numerous rivers in Jharkhand, which are deviating from their natural courses due to rampant sand mining activities, driven by the insatiable demands of the perpetrators and unquenchable desires of overpopulation. The lines illustrate:

“More ravenous still is their appetite,
They plough her bosom day and night,
And with their spades they dig mercilessly
To rip and gouge out from her body
Chunks of earth, red and meaty.” (Kerketta, 14-18)

The poet, here as a daughter of mother nature laments over the exploitation of mother river by the industrial activities associated with sand mining and dam projects. Jacinta has grown up witnessing the sufferings of nature and the miserable predicament of Adivasi people. She involved herself in the struggle of the vast adivasi society to preserve their land, forests, rivers, languages, and heritage and culture, which she expresses in her poetry. “Tribals of various regions of India know very well that there is only one path to survival and that path is the ecological one, of harmony between man and nature. They believe that all nature is sacrosanct, that the earth itself as a living organism is capable of experiencing pain and pleasure” (Chandra and Das, 32). The pursuit of a luxurious, modern and materialistic lifestyle has led certain selfish groups to become neglectful and irresponsible in their responsibilities towards mother nature. The industrial machineries indiscriminately and ruthlessly grab and damage her all organs, ultimately leading to her death in order to plunder valuable chunks like sand and stone.

As the poet Kerketta articulates, “They plough her bosom day and night” (line - 15). The agonies experienced by all living species is evident, as the water of the river not only supports the livelihood of the Adivasi people but also serves as a habitat of various aquatic species. The poet’s depiction of agony, in this regard, not only human centred but eco-centred, as water sources provides habitats for a diverse range of aquatic species. It is also the home to a large number of flora and fauna. The invasion of the industrial machinery and constant mining activities has adversely devastated the river’s healthy ecosystem.

In another poem, “Bloodstained rivers”, the poet depicts the ecological pangs through the picture of crying rivers and forests over the loss of trees. This poem holds an account of the ecological disruption occurring within the forest of Saranda. The anguish experienced by the felled trees profoundly affected both, the forest ecosystem and its associated biodiversity, including its flora and fauna. The dust, emissions of smoke from coal mining, and abundance of iron ore, have turned the verdant hues of the green forest to a reddish tint. The ruthless invasion of heavy machinery for iron ore extraction has rampantly devastated the ecological balance of the forest and diminished the biodiversity in this region. The picture reveals the bonding and interconnected relationship between human beings and nature. The air is polluted, and toxic rainfall worsen the plight, as harmful substances are integrated with the precipitation, indicating severe repercussions of constant mining activities. The dust of iron ore mixed with the water of the rivers, has resulted in a red and toxic contamination that poses a significant threat to aquatic life. The mourning over the loss of ecological equilibrium is intensified by ascribing the human qualities to the natural world. By using the personification of the natural elements, as illustrated by the phrase ‘the waters drenched in blood bewail’, the poet tries to set up an emotional connection between the reader and natural environment. Furthermore, with a purpose to brood over the relationship between nature and human beings. The poem depicts the significance role of the trees for nature and for Adivasi people. As the poet portrays:

“And the waters drenched in blood bewail,

Weeping on the shoulders of riverbanks,

And the entire forest sees red.” (Kerketta, 5 -7)

The invasion of heavy machinery and constant mining activities has disrupted and damaged the ecosystem of the forest. The emissions of toxic pollutants resulting from mining activities has significantly degraded the quality of the air, thereby threatening the physical and mental health of the forest ecosystem, including its plants and animals, along with the indigenous communities residing in this region. Moreover, the sound of explosions in mines has severely destroyed the peaceful life of the forest. The intrusion of state machinery into tribal belts has significantly disrupted the local people's management of forest resources. As a consequence, the marginalized status of the impoverished has intensified, resulting in their profound disconnection from their natural surroundings, as Ramachandra Guha noted in his book *Environmentalism: A Global History* (156). The indigenous people are often marginalized, dispossessed from their ancestral lands, face socioeconomic disadvantages and are often perceived as mere victims of oppression. They lost their cordial link with nature and have to live in polluted areas caused by mining activities in various regions of Jharkhand. Such an environment has resulted in health hazards where children and adults equally die of sickness and disease (Khakhlari, 169). The sufferings of nature and Adivasi people have been depicted by the poet in the poem “The Blossom of Saranda”:

“Deep in blissful slumber

The flower's perfume

Startles and awakens,

When the stench of machines

Invades the senses

And ears scream in splitting pain

From the noise of explosions.” (Kerketta, 1-7)

In the poems of Jacinta Karketta reveals the interconnection between environmental degradation and the resulting ecological anguish. She has witnessed the profound and direct impact of environmental destruction upon the lives of people who regard nature as their mother. The Adivasi people are conscious of the ecological knowledge, which is rooted in the interdependent relationship that exists between natural environment and human beings. From time immemorial, they have coexisted harmonious and mutual relationship with the natural environment. They have acquired and accumulated the knowledge of the interrelationship between human beings and nature. They do not subscribe to the practice of idol worship, as they regard nature as a sacred entity that deserves reverence. For Adivasi people, natural elements such as land, water, forest, and mountains are revered as deities. Their way of life is deeply interrelated with the forest life. They do not exploit and degrade nature, as they believe in maintaining sanctity of nature, which indirectly helps to preservation of natural environment from destruction. Nature provides them, not only the basic elements but also food, shelter, and livelihoods. Their bonding with the natural world is profoundly ingrained. However, the poet expresses sorrow regarding the deterioration of this pure relationship, which has been exploited by the self- serving industrial groups in the pursuit of development. As the poet says:

“No footsteps more are heard,
Plodding along towards the fields,
For addicted now are those feet
To chase after trucks laden with

Along the road of the PANEM mines.” (Kerketta, 6-10)

The pangs of displacement and disconnection can be felt through the lines of the poem, “The dust of development”. The poet has depicted picture of deserted fields where there are no signs of farmers. The fields are left alone to accomplish the process of development. As a member of the Adivasi community, Kerketta possesses profound understanding of the challenges faced by this group. She vividly portrays the picture of agonies by addressing the issues of environmental degradation and involuntary displacement of indigenous people. They share symbiotic relationship with nature, however, when their habitats are demolished or sometimes, they are forcefully expelled from their natural surroundings, they experience a sense of disorientation within urban landscapes and their work in the mining become a Hobson’s choice. Initially, those feet were accustomed to walk and toil in the fields for the purpose of crops cultivation, however, those feet have now become addicted to pursuing trucks laden with coal. The loss of ancestral lands has led to a profound sense of mourning among the Adivasi community, as they reflect on the disruption of natural environment and their blissful home. According to Merriam - Webster Online Dictionary, ‘Ache’ is “to suffer a usually dull, persistent pain” or “to experience a painful eagerness or yearning.” (<https://www.merriamwebster.com/dictionary/ache>) Displacement is characterized as “the act or process of ‘displacing’: the state of being displaced”.

(<https://www.merriamwebster.com/dictionary/displace>). It generally occurs in two forms: physical and psychological. Displacement not only denotes the relocation of individuals from one place to another, but it also implies a sense of uprootedness. A displaced person is deprived of his/her place taken over by other people or forces. (Displacement Ache in the Selected Poems of Meena Kandasamy and Rupri Kaur)

The exploitation and disruption of natural environments, and execution of marginalized Adivasi people from their ancestral home under the guise of progress, is fundamentally illogical to them. The profound agonies experienced by indigenous people from being deprived and uprooted of one's own loved land and home is apparent in the poem, "O City". Within the work, the city remains unable to provide answer to the questions posed by those afflicted people.

In their paper, Reading Jacinta Kerketta: the Voice of Contemporary Jharkhand, Bhattacharjee and Singh articulate that the Adivasis feel compelled to ask what this "development" means and for whom it is being executed. They never asked for it in the first place. The Adivasi people departing from their forest-based lifestyles pose a significant question to the city this pertinent question - whether the city has ever been "wrenched from their very roots" like they have been in the pursuit of what is often referred to as "progress"? (Karketta 2016: 5-6).

"Leaving behind their homes,

Their soil, their bales of straw,

Fleeing the roof over their heads, they often ask

O, city!

Are you ever wrenched by the very roots

In the name of so-called progress?" (Kerketta, 1-6)

Another poem, "The jungle says", from "The land of the Roots" (Kerketta, 2025), portrays nature as a mentor, guardian and protector of the people coexist harmoniously within the jungle. Karketta illustrated how the natural environment enables a man residing in the jungle to acquire the skill of dance from rain, growth and generosity from trees. Moreover, in the lap of blithe spirit of nature out of joy songs come out from the innermost being of the jungle man with the same spontaneity as mushrooms spring forth from the forest floor. The role of nature as a

mentor has been profoundly embedded in their lifestyle. The poet asserts that the jungle consistently acts as a defender of its people, ensuring their survival by providing the essential elements necessary for their sustenance and livelihood. The jungle conveys that it is difficult to kill its inhabitants residing within the jungle, sufferings experienced by the jungle itself as well as its people is perceived. The jungle not only sustains the life of its people but also sustains their identity. The relationship between human beings and nature is characterized by mutual dependence and interconnectedness.

“The jungle says

An ocean it can never be,

For in its merging into the ocean

Every river is stripped of its identity.

The jungle alone sustains,

Each with its identity it maintains.” (Kerketta, 8-13)

However, the last stanza of the poem gives a painful account.

“And so, they build roads

Leading out of the jungle's cover.” (Kerketta, 16-17)

The lines illustrate the pangs of the jungle for its flora and fauna. In the poem the poet personifies the jungle as a voice that recounts the narrative of agonies felt by the natural world including its flora and fauna as well as the Adivasi people. Which is inflicted by a self – interested and callous group of individuals, indicated by the phrase, “The Jungle Says”. It illustrates that, in order to access and exploit mineral resources located within the jungle, the self – serving powerful groups engage in the relentless mining activities and construction of

roadways, a process that involves the merciless excavation and disruption of ecosystem, resulting in the degradation of the jungle's ecological balance. Furthermore, it is paradoxical that in their pursuit of progress, they are consistently constructing the road of destruction toward their own demise. The industrial heavy machinery exerts a significant impact on human life, often leading to the degradation of the natural environment and the habitats of various species, including Adivasi communities, thereby causing displacement and loss of life.

Conclusion:

To conclude, studying the ecological agonies of Kerketta's selected poems is an attempt to highlight the impact of human actions on the environment and spread environmental awareness among people. The poet develops the concern for environmental degradation is omniscience, which illustrates alarming imagery that stems from industrialization, urbanization and the unprecedented, avaricious expansion of self-interested elite groups. In her verses, she advocates for the rights of Adivasi communities and the preservation of the natural environment. Her work highlights the ecological distress encountered by these marginalized groups alongside the deterioration of natural ecosystem and biodiversity. She attempts to figure out how cruel selfish group of people have imposed limitations, bondage and inhuman treatment on the green earth. The poet seems to indicate very straightforwardly and prophetically advocated the degrading relation between nature and human beings. It implies that humanity must express gratitude and respect in its relationship with nature in order avert the looming threat of total annihilation of human civilization. Through the depiction of agonies, suffering and silent cry and protest in the poems of Kerketta, this study exhibits an urge to take environmental responsibility to conserve nature, biodiversity, ecosystem and natural resources as well as to rethink their interdependent and interconnected relationship with nature from the perspective of ecocriticism.

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